

Multimodal, Non-Destructive Testing (NDT) Molecular Characterisations -As a Strategic Approach for Defect Detection & Quality Assessment in Polymers- A Perspective towards Quantum Sensing in Plastic Recycling.

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1. Abstract:

Here, we present a novel concept for a multimodal sensing strategy to detect and quantify defects in a polymer system, thereby calculating the percentage of recycled plastic content in a random plastic product. The technique combines various physical characteristic responses from the samples in a non-destructive manner, in contrast to the existing destructive methods. This strategy provides a scalable solution for sustainable plastic reuse, enabling rapid and non-destructive quality assurance, supporting the circular economy.

2. Keywords: Multimodal sensing, Non-destructive testing, Plastic recycling, Polymer defect, Quantum sensing, Material quality assessment, Defect detection, Circular economy.

3. Overview/Introduction:

The escalating environmental challenges posed by plastic pollution, driven by increased consumption and inadequate disposal practices, necessitate effective recycling strategies to mitigate harm while maintaining the integrity of the material. Maintaining the quality of recycled plastics is crucial, as repeated processing leads to the degradation of polymer molecular chains, which adversely affects their chemical and mechanical properties. This degradation limits the number of recycling steps a plastic material can undergo without compromising its performance in a commercial scenario where the ratio of recycled to pristine materials significantly affects the product performance.

While conventional analytical methods, such as Thermogravimetric Analysis TGA, Differential Scanning Calorimetry DSC or Nuclear Magnetic Resonance NMR offer precise compositional analysis, their requirement for costly, time-intensive, and destructive sampling hinders routine quality assessment. To address these limitations, we are discussing an innovative multimodal, non-destructive testing strategy that can rapidly evaluate the quality of plastics, including the recycled content within the finished products, by accessing their various physical properties, such as mechanical/ (micro/nano mechanical), triboelectric, optical, viscoelastic, dielectric, or chemical response signals.

The recycled contents can be perceived as various accumulated defects in the material system and can be quantified as we quantify the defects. By integrating multiple sensing modalities into a single domain -including dielectric spectroscopies, viscoelastic testing, photothermal/photoacoustic spectroscopies, micro/nano mechanical responses, triboelectric signals, electrical/magnetic transport properties, thermal/optical responses, etc.- this approach aims to determine the defect density of the material system quantitatively and hence the recycled content, offering a promising pathway towards enhanced material quality monitoring and future integration with quantum sensing technologies with plastic recycling applications to support the sustainability and the circular economy^[1-6].

4. Methodology/Approach:

Preliminary experimental verification of the concepts is conducted using plastic samples collected from everyday products, commercially available samples, lab-fabricated blends and custom-made specially fabricated samples with varying percentages of recycled plastic content. Compared the results with pristine virgin polymer samples with different types of plastics- type-1 to type-7

The primary experimental techniques used are:

- **Dielectric impedance spectroscopy**
- **Triboelectric contact testing**
- **Electrical transport and Magnetism**
- **Acoustic studies**
- **Photothermal/Photoacoustic studies**
- **Viscoelastic properties**
- **Defect Modulation as a self-referencing technique- through ‘Electrets’.**
- **Micro/ Nano mechanics- The AFM force curve analysis**
- **The storage and loss modulus**
- **Combination techniques- presence of electric/magnetic fields**

The physical property measurement signals that arise from the core material's response are used to detect and quantify abnormalities and defects in the material system. In the case of plastic polymers, these defects can be a direct indication of the recycled contents in the material. The defect density is calculated separately using each technique and integrated into a single standard format. The percentage of recycled content is calculated from the defect density.

Figure 1: Schematic of the concept of multimodal sensing device probe strategy in the context of plastic quality testing- showing the probe with various signal responses integrated into a single platform sensor probe receiving signals directly from a product and analyzing the quantity of the recycled content.

5. Results and future studies:

The preliminary experiments validate the feasibility and sensitivity of the proposed multimodal approach across a range of polymer types and recycled content percentages. The results have been verified using various plastic samples from different contexts, including samples collected from day-to-day products, commercially available polymer samples, and plastic samples collected from other laboratories. The results are verified and standardized with custom-made samples with varying recycled contents, such as - recycled content of 0%- pristine polymer, recycled content of 5%, 10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, 50%, 60%, 70%, 80% 90% and finally 100% recycled samples. The experiments have been carried out using all types of plastic polymers, including type-1 polymer PET/PETE, type-2 polymer HDPE, type-3 polymer PVC, type-4 polymer LDPE, type-5 polymer PP, type-6 polymer PS, and type-7 polymers ABS/PMMA/PC.

The preliminary experiments verified the innovative ideas mentioned earlier. The studies can be used to manufacture a multimodal sensing device probe for detecting and quantifying the percentage of recycled content in a given plastic product using non-destructive physical characterization methods. The estimated results presented here can be further analyzed and refined through computational methods, simulations and modelling, and AI/ML-assisted tools, paving the way for enhanced accuracy and deeper insights.

The discussed sensing approach is extended to the quantum sensing technologies for plastic recycling. Moreover, the results open up new perspectives on many complex quantum phenomena exhibited by polymers in general and can be extended to a broader research perspective.

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7. Disclosure and Data Availability:

This preprint is submitted as a defensive disclosure to establish the author's prior conceptual contributions and ideas developed from confidential internal discussions and preliminary experimental studies. To respect existing confidentiality agreements, no proprietary or raw experimental data are included. The author's affiliation is verifiable through the University at Buffalo (SUNY) Department of Chemical and Biological Engineering alumni records. This disclosure intends to provide a public record of these innovations while maintaining professionalism and respect for the parties involved.

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